

Earth Peace Coin, q-IPFS, Code Units(C.U) and NFTs in Landscape architecture.

Dr bheemaiah anil k, synergy robotics bc
Seattle WA 98125
coderdojostpaul2@gmail.com

Abstract.

BIM templates, (“Building Information Modeling” 2006) with GIS in the Metaverse With a digital blueprint in DPA, are stored in a hypothetical quantum web3 architecture, with code units, or CU of the digital twins, defined by the blueprints tokenized as non fungible tokens for IPFS(Liu et al. 2024) or q-IPFS, with ethereum.

This defines a newer smart contract on the ethereum virtual machine for minting NFTs(Costa, La Cava, and Tagarelli 2023) as code units in a metaverse of evolutionary transcription mechanisms for digital assets.

KeyWords: digital assets, NFT, non fungible, BIM, Minty, Ethereum, DPA, quantum storage, web3, DiFi, DApp, CU or Code Unit, IPFS, q-IPFS, metaverse, quantum storage, AI4Good.

Fig 1. (“Photos: Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Then and Now - Global Times,” n.d.) A collection of images linked from a public domain web source, cited below, of Hiroshima, Then and Now, a proof of Akira Miyawaki’s philosophy, that nature restores itself, as if human action did not exist.

Core Content.

1. Definition of the q-IPFS file system as quantum hybrid storage with a blockchain.
2. Illustration of NFTs for digital assets, namely BIMs of landscape architecture of Miyawakis, as a digital blueprint, an asset exosystem tokenized as non fungible tokens stored on IPFS and minted as NFTs with OpenSea.
3. Design of the Earth Peace crypto on q-IPFS and a smart contract on Ethereum.

Introduction.

Philosophy of Akira Miyawaki.

“May the force be with you”, in a new Jedi religion, or restoration, of that very force of nature , of that star Helios, closest to us, is the neo-heliocentrism, an engineering of native flora based forestry, with restorative ecology and agroforestry practices, several practitioners have practiced the technique of the green space as beyond the last shangri la, the return to an engineered human approximation of primary forests - completed by nature itself.

In a two world model of a one with potential theoretic formulations, with a height based potentiation, similar to theories of rain forest models, is a restorative two world approach to Miyawaki Landscaping(A. D. Bheemaiah, n.d.) in a transition from a size based BIM model to true mereotopology and primary growth with the natural forces of restoration.

IPFS Minty.

Minty,(GitHub - yusefnapora/minty: a minimal...) is a minimal application for the automated minting of a digital asset using the IPFS file system. In a practical application to minting Code Units or C.U on ETH, we design a blueprint for each digital asset to be transcribed into code units for carbon trading and the minting of NFTs of the digital twins as digital assets.

Code Units.

Code Units for an atomicity of assets in the metaverse and an atomicity of digital process automation, with an evolutionary programming paradigm.

Code Units (CUs) represent the atomicity of automation within this architecture, serving as encapsulated digital processes for automation and data management. CUs are transcribed from BIM templates and serve as the base layer for automating asset creation, storage, and replication across the metaverse.

CUs as NFTs: Each CU is stored as an NFT on q-IPFS, accessible within the Ethereum ecosystem. This enables a marketplace where digital twins, such as Miyawaki forest elements, can be bought, sold, and transferred while retaining IP and usage rights.

Digital DNA of Assets: Analogous to biological DNA, each CU includes a “digital genome” representing the asset’s characteristics, encoded for evolutionary adjustments. This allows for variability and adaptation within the metaverse, creating a dynamic environment for landscape assets.

Analogous to Soul Machines, Digital DNA, (“Soul Machines Gallery,” n.d.) is a DNA applicable to a MAC formulation in MFA II design. Digital Assets are blueprinted as machine DNA and transcription parametrics as part of the restorative ecology of virtual land, digital twin of real estate assets.

In (IaC, CaC, MaC)(A. K. Bheemaiah 2019) as the description of any manifold in the computable realm are code units defined for web2/web3/monolithic or storage based manifolds of the metaverse or threads of code woven to a fabric of the metaverse or as legacy code deployed in DevOPs frameworks with build automation.

IaC is automated in the atomicity of cloud functions, for each cloud function, IaC is defined with a resource indicator for the thread, web2/web3 allocation and the use of functoids with code generation APIs

Digital twins in the metaverse.

Several sites now let you develop, sell and buy virtual land, in a digital twin of real estate as NFTs, Miyawaki planning as a collection of BIMs on virtual land could be a way towards NFT based virtual estate in restorative ecology, creating a value addition in a smart contract towards a newer crypto of restoration, the earth peace. The storage could be a hybrid quantum web3, rather than the present web3.

Current solutions.

Virtual land as assets can be traded at several sites[], in the creation of a web2 and web3 based metaverse, is the present browser based rendering of 3D models of architecture, using Modelo Architecture and BIM models integrated to a voronoi[] embedded in GIS in the metaverse.

Implementation.

1. Generating the machine genome, transcription for BIM object templates.
2. Randomized instantiation of a particular sized asset from template.
3. Generation of a NFT token from the asset and conversion to rivet , autocad format.

4. Addition of the BIM object to voronoi of Miyawaki Landscape, and conversion of the virtual land asset to an NFT.

Broccoli Tree Creator, a premium extension for Unity as an example.

Broccoli Tree Generator(GitHub - cyberbotics/webots: Webots R...) is a procedural tree generator for Unity with two generators, a grammar based and a L System based, which is directly amenable to a genome representation, especially as a cartesian , parametric and a natural 4 base scheme.

The Transcriptional mechanisms lead to the standard Unity based rendering, with textures, UV maps and wind flow models. The Assets can be readily exported from Unity to Rivet formats and the GLB format for NFT creation.

Unity allows for the NFTs to be created in GIS, tokenized to virtual land, GIS in the Metaverse. The use of DLP based 4k projection, leads to augmented reality and a true Metaverse on a wall surface.

We illustrate this Miyawaki with a live wall of Bodhi and MahaBodhi trees, depicted in the Metaverse by a lattice trellis with vertical gardening of Bodhi trees.

The NFT assets are vertical gardening pots with Bodhi plants each randomized from a machine genome.

The Tree Editor on Unity, SpeedTree and other Tree Editing Tools.

Trees and Plants, in unity can be expressed with data structures with nodes indicating branches and leaves with material properties with maps.

The cartesian genome is [[b],[n],[map]]

Future work.

Problem Statement.

Creation of a Miyawaki Voronoi in the Metaverse using BIM assets and GIS data, on virtual land. Use of NFTs to tokenize each BIM asset and the virtual land on ETH, using Modelo Architecture.["Best Free 3D Model Viewer & Editor," n.d.]

Problem Statement

Architecture of a quantum blockchain analogous to IPFS and filecoin, called q-IPFS, using Code Units. Code Units are an atomicity of automation, transcending deployed code on web2 or web3. A transcendence of a container based automated build and deployment is transcription from a genetic blueprint for code based on evolutionary programming paradigms.

In code units, billing is neither by man hours or by material, but by a tokenized equity in code units, or C.U.

C.U's are traded with ETH, and are tradable for carbon credits.

Code Units also represent content and digital land. We illustrate this design paradigm with the architecture of a new quantum storage called q-IPFS, using q-filecoin to host an ecological metaverse, for rewilding.

The zeros of the zeta function and riemannian hypothesis.

The earth peace crypto, has a proof of stake and consensus algorithm defined by the zeta function.

The Earth Peace Coin is a cryptocurrency that provides value aligned with ecological impact, specifically carbon sequestration and biodiversity restoration. Built on Ethereum, Earth Peace Coin leverages a Proof of Stake algorithm governed by the zeros of the Riemann zeta function. This mathematical foundation reduces volatility while creating a consensus protocol geared toward ecological sustainability.

The PoS and Consensus algorithms are in development and the topic of a future publication.

Conclusion

This innovation integrates Code Units (CUs), q-IPFS, Earth Peace Coin, and NFT-based digital assets to bring ecological principles into digital architecture. By combining BIM modeling, evolutionary programming, and blockchain, it provides a comprehensive framework for scalable, eco-focused landscape management. Through this approach, landscape architecture can transition into a hybrid realm of digital and real-world applications, fostering biodiversity and supporting the creation of environmentally responsible digital spaces in the metaverse.

- "Best Free 3D Model Viewer & Editor." n.d. Accessed November 15, 2024.
<https://www.modelo.io>.
- Bheemaiah, Anil Dr. n.d. "Amazon.com: UOL A 621 Miyawaki Landscaping eBook : Dr Bheemaiah, Anil: Kindle Store." Accessed November 15, 2024.
https://www.amazon.com/UOL-Miyawaki-Landscaping-Anil-Bheemaiah-ebook/dp/B09CP52JJF/ref=sr_1_1?s=digital-text&sr=1-1.
- Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar. 2019. "Singularity#1 and MFA II. Singularität Nr. 1 Und MFA II," August.
<https://doi.org/10.31224/osf.io/3ghkf>.
- "Building Information Modeling." 2006. Wikimedia Foundation, Inc. February 6, 2006.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Building_information_modeling.
- Costa, Davide, Lucio La Cava, and Andrea Tagarelli. 2023. "Unraveling the NFT Economy: A Comprehensive Collection of Non-Fungible Token Transactions and Metadata." *Data in Brief* 51 (December):109749.
- Liu, Tong, Si-Nga Lai, Xiaochen Yuan, Yue Liu, and Chan-Tong Lam. 2024. "A Novel Blockchain-Watermarking Mechanism Utilizing Interplanetary File System and Fast Walsh Hadamard Transform." *iScience* 27 (9): 110821.
- "Photos: Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Then and Now - Global Times." n.d. Accessed August 26, 2022. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/galleries/163.html>.
- "Soul Machines Gallery." n.d. Soul Machines_042324. Accessed November 15, 2024.
<https://www.soulmachines.com/soul-machines-studio>.